

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY AND MOLECULAR CONSTITUTION. PART III. HETEROPOLY MOLYBDATES AND TUNGSTATES WITH POLYVALENT METAL ATOMS IN THE COMPLEX

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A number of compounds containing molybdic acid anhydride and various bi, ter, and quadrivalent metal oxides, besides alkali or alkaline earth metal oxides, described by earlier workers, were prepared and examined magneto-chemically with a view to determining their constitution and the valence state of the central metal atoms involved in their formation. A similar study of a complex sodium manganese paratungstate with quadrivalent manganese has also been made. The results have led to the conclusion that these compounds should be regarded as salts of 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid or its derivative, with the metal atoms forming the centre of octahedral co-ordination complexes either of the penetration or the associated type. Only in the case of the nickel compound which contains 9 MoO₃ for each nickel atom, a different formulation as a double salt of 6-molybdenum and 12-molybdenum heteropolyacids, or as a salt of a new 9-molybdenum heteropolyacid, has been necessary. Hence, all of these, with the exclusion of the above mentioned nickel compound, might be included in the class of silico-, phospho-, arseno-, iodo- or telluro-molybdates, as already suggested by Rosenheim. The tungsten compound also can be represented as a derivative of 6-tungsten heteropolyacid salt.

Heteropoly molybdates and tungstates with quadri- and quinquivalent metalloids like silicon, phosphorus and arsenic are quite well known. They are salts of the complex 12-molybdenum or 12-tungsten heteropolyacid of the general formula, H_{12-n}[Me(X₂O₇)₆].aq., where X = Mo or W. Iodine and tellurium also similarly form 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid complexes of the formula H₆[I(MoO₄)₆].aq. and H₆[Te(MoO₄)₆].aq, with septivalent iodine and sexivalent tellurium respectively. Besides, a large number of compounds containing molybdic acid anhydride and various trivalent metallic oxides, in addition to alkali metal and alkaline earth metal oxides, and in some cases even oxides of silver, mercury and lead, have been described by various workers (Struve, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1854, i, 61 453; Friedheim and Keller, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 4301; Markwald, Dissertation, Berlin, 1895; Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 692; Rosenheim and Schwer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1914, 89, 224; Barbieri, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1914, 23, 328; Kurnakow, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1899, 14, 113). They seem to form an isomorphous series of the general formula, 3R₂O. Me₂O₃. 12MoO₃. xH₂O. Compounds have also been described with oxides of metals in the quadrivalent state (Ni, Co and Mn) of the formula, 3R₂O(RO).MeO₂.9MoO₃.aq. (Hall, *loc. cit.*). Furthermore, compounds with oxides of metals in the bivalent state of the general formula, 3R₂O.2MeO.12MoO₃.aq., (Me = Cu, Ni, Mn, Co, Mg, Ca), have also been prepared (Barbieri, *Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1914, 23, II, 357; Marckwald, *loc. cit.* Rosenheim, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1916, 96, 147).

Some of the earlier workers (cf. Friedheim and Samelson, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1900, 24, 67) regarded these compounds as double molybdates, similar to double sulphates like alums. But the work of Hall (*loc. cit.*) and of Rosenheim (*loc. cit.*) have demonstrated that they should be represented as salts of complex inorganic acids composed of the oxide of the metal concerned and MoO₃. They based their conclusion on the strong colour possessed by the compounds, the constant ratio of the oxide of the

heavy metal to MoO_3 in all their salts, the preparation of the free acid in some cases, and a study of the properties of the substances in aqueous solution. The complexes, composed of the oxides of the type, MeO and MeO_2 , were considered by Rosenheim as derivatives of paramolybdates, resembling the salts of 6-molybdenum heteropolyacids, like telluro- and iodomolybdic acids, in accordance with his view of the constitution of paramolybdates on the basis of Werner's theory. The constitution of these compounds were represented by him as follows :

Complexes with MeO_2 cannot, however, be represented either as salts of 6-molybdenum or 12-molybdenum heteropolyacid. They can, however, be regarded as double compounds of 6-molybdenum and 12-molybdenum heteropolyacid salts, or better as a new type of 9-molybdenum heteropoly complex salt, viz.

With a view to examining the nature of these complexes and the valency of their central metal atoms we have prepared a number of these complex metal molybdates, particularly those containing the metals of the first transitional series as the central atoms, and have measured their magnetic moments. Sodium, potassium and barium salts of a complex manganic-tungstic acid with quadrivalent manganese (Just, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 3619) have also been prepared and the magnetic susceptibility of the sodium salt determined. The results are described and discussed below.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1. *Ammonium nickel^{IV} molybdate* was prepared according to the method described by Hall (*loc. cit.*) by oxidising a boiling solution of ammonium paramolybdate and nickel sulphate with ammonium persulphate. The substance was purified by recrystallising several times from hot water, containing a little ammonium persulphate. [Found: NH_3 , 6.30; Ni, 3.58; MoO_3 , 78.83; O(active), 0.975; H_2O (by diff.), 6.0. $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}, \text{NiO}_2, 9\text{MoO}_3, 5.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires NH_3 , 6.21; Ni, 3.58; MoO_3 , 78.90; O(active), 0.974; H_2O , 6.03 per cent].

Magnetic susceptibility of the substance was measured by Gouy's method in a magnetic field of strength 10.16×10^3 gauss.

$$t = 24^\circ; \chi_g = -0.0571 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = -93.76 \times 10^{-6}.$$

After correction for diamagnetism, $\chi_A = 1.74 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_B = 0.065$.

The substance forms fine purple-black crystals.

The *barium salt* was prepared from a solution of the ammonium salt by precipitation with barium chloride. A brown crystalline precipitate was obtained. [Found: Ba, 20.14; Ni, 2.77; MoO_3 , 63.10; O(active), 0.769; H_2O (by difference from the loss by ignition and the amount of oxygen), 9.49. $3\text{BaO}, \text{NiO}_2, 9\text{MoO}_3, 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ba, 20.14; Ni, 2.87; MoO_3 , 63.37; O(active), 0.782; H_2O , 9.68 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = -0.2001 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = -219.3 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = -41.5 \times 10^{-6}.$$

2. *Potassium cobaltic^{III} molybdate* (6-MoO_3) was prepared by oxidising a boiling solution of a mixture of potassium paramolybdate and cobalt sulphate with potassium persulphate. The substance was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. [Found:

K, 9.16; Co, 4.47; MoO₃, 66.95; O(active), 0.57; H₂O (from total loss by ignition and that of oxygen), 15.70. 3K₂O, Co₂O₃, 12MoO₃, 22.5H₂O requires K, 9.08; Co, 4.58; MoO₃, 66.94; O(active), 0.62; H₂O, 15.67 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = -0.446 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_m = -115.1 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 90.6 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 0.58.$$

The substance forms crystals of green colour. Hall (*loc. cit.*) obtained a different product by this method with quadrivalent cobalt of the composition, 3K₂O, CoO₂, 9MoO₃, 6.5H₂O.

3. *Potassium cobaltic^{III} molybdate* (5-MoO₃) was prepared from a boiling solution of cobalt acetate (3.5 g.), potassium paramolybdate (10 g.) and potassium persulphate (6 g.). The violet precipitate, formed at the beginning, dissolved on continuous heating. The green solution, so obtained, was freed from the suspended impurities by immediate filtration. The clear solution on cooling gave light green, sparingly soluble micro-crystals together with some white needles of potassium trimolybdate. The mixture was filtered and the white crystals of trimolybdate were removed by rubbing with the mother-liquor. The product was washed and dried as usual (cf. Friedheim and Keller, *loc. cit.*). [Found: K, 11.05; Co, 5.40; MoO₃, 67.48; O(active), 0.73; H₂O (from the loss of weight by ignition and that of oxygen), 11.60. 3K₂O, Co₂O₃, 10MoO₃, 13.5H₂O requires K, 11.0; Co, 5.46; MoO₃, 67.52; O(active), 0.74; H₂O, 11.54 per cent].

The substance was found to be diamagnetic. χ_g at 30° = 0.0; $\chi_A = +110 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_s = 0.52$.

The corresponding *ammonium salt* was prepared by treating a mixture of cobaltous acetate (1.55 g. in 40 c.c. water) and ammonium paramolybdate (7.5 g. in 30 c.c. water) with 10 c.c. of 18% hydrogen peroxide solution in the cold. The mixture was gently warmed when the solution became dark green at the end. On cooling, small quantities of 6-molybdenum compound were precipitated along with the dark green crystals. These latter were first separated by mechanical means and then by recrystallization from water at 70°. The crystals were washed and dried as usual (cf. Friedheim and Keller, *loc. cit.*). [Found: NH₃, 3.57; Co, 5.99; MoO₃, 73.84; O(active), 0.812; H₂O, (by diff.), 12.28. 2(NH₄)₂O, Co₂O₃, 10MoO₃, 12H₂O requires NH₃, 3.53; Co, 6.01; MoO₃, 74.78; O(active), 0.814; H₂O, 11.21 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = 0; \chi_A = +76 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 0.43.$$

4. *Ammonium chromic molybdate* was prepared by boiling a solution of ammonium chrome alum with ammonium paramolybdate. The rose-red crystalline product was recrystallized several times from hot water (cf. Hall, *loc. cit.*). [Found: NH₃, 4.61; Cr, 4.07; MoO₃, 67.81; H₂O (by diff.), 19.20. 3.5(NH₄)₂O, Cr₂O₃, 12MoO₃, 27H₂O requires NH₃, 4.67; Cr, 4.08; MoO₃, 67.77; H₂O, 19.07 per cent].

$$t = 31^\circ; \chi_g = 5.17 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_m = 12710 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 6509 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 4.0.$$

5. *Ammonium ferric molybdate* was prepared from ammonium paramolybdate and ferric ammonium alum (cf. Hall, *loc. cit.*). The substance forms almost white crystals. [Found: NH₃, 4.32; Fe, 4.74; MoO₃, 72.80; H₂O (from total loss by ignition and the amount of ammonia), 13.96. 3(NH₄)₂O, Fe₂O₃, 12MoO₃, 11H₂O requires NH₃, 4.30; Fe, 4.73; MoO₃, 72.81; H₂O, 13.87 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = 11.73 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_m = 27790 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A \text{ (corr.)} = 14013.5 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 5.85.$$

6. *Barium manganiv-molybdate* was prepared from a boiling solution of a mixture of potassium molybdate (4 g.), molybdic acid anhydride (6 g.), and hydrated manganese sulphate (1g.) by oxidation with bromine water. The excess of molybdic acid and other suspended impurities were removed by filtration. The clear solution, on cooling, deposited the crystals of potassium manganiv-molybdate. A solution of this salt, on treatment with that of barium chloride, gave a light brown micro-crystalline precipitate of the barium salt. This was washed and dried as usual (cf. Hall, *loc. cit.*). [Found: Ba, 20.15; Mn, 2.60; MoO₃, 62.87; O(active), 0.753; H₂O (by diff.), 9.75. 3BaO, MnO₂, 9MoO₃, 12H₂O requires Ba, 20.13; Mn, 2.67; MoO₃, 62.98; O(active), 0.77; H₂O, 9.53 per cent].

$$t = 28^\circ; \chi_g = 2.93 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = 6036 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 6211 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 3.88.$$

7. *Ammonium nickel molybdate* was prepared by boiling a solution of ammonium paramolybdate with nickel sulphate. On cooling the green solution, light green crystals of the substance separated (cf. Rosenheim, *loc. cit.*). [Found: NH₃, 5.78; Ni, 4.97; MoO₃, 73.20; H₂O (from the loss by ignition and ammonia), 11.66. 3(NH₄)₂O, NiO, 6MoO₃, 7.5H₂O requires NH₃, 5.77; Ni, 4.97; MoO₃, 73.21; H₂O, 11.63 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = 3.49 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = 4109 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 4223 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 3.21.$$

8. *Ammonium cupric molybdate* was obtained as bluish white microscopic crystals from a cold solution of copper sulphate and ammonium paramolybdate (cf. Rosenheim, *loc. cit.*). [Found: NH₃, 5.62; Cu, 5.30; MoO₃, 71.66; H₂O (from the difference of loss by ignition and ammonia), 13.20. 2(NH₄)₂O, CuO, 6MoO₃, 6H₂O requires NH₃, 5.62; Cu, 5.24; MoO₃, 71.47; H₂O, 13.36 per cent].

$$t = 30^\circ; \chi_g = 1.30 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = 1506 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 1602 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 1.98.$$

9. *Ammonium manganous molybdate* was obtained from an acid solution of manganous chloride (10 g.) and a saturated solution of ammonium paramolybdate (24 g.) in the form of fine red, silky crystals, which turned yellow after some days. [Found: NH₃, 4.35; Mn, 4.65; MoO₃, 73.70; H₂O (by diff.), 13.61. 1.5(NH₄)₂O, MnO, 6MoO₃, 9H₂O requires NH₃, 4.34; Mn, 4.65; MoO₃, 73.53; H₂O, 13.79 per cent].

$$t = 25^\circ; \chi_g = 17.36 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = 20398 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 20500 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 7.0.$$

10. *Ammonium cobaltous molybdate* was prepared from a cold concentrated solution of cobalt chloride (10 g.) and a cold saturated solution of ammonium paramolybdate. Light violet, microscopic crystals separated after a few days (Rosenheim, *loc. cit.*). [Found: NH₃, 4.20; Co, 6.45; MoO₃, 74.11; H₂O (by difference), 13.04. 1.5(NH₄)₂O, CoO, 6MoO₃, 8.5H₂O requires NH₃, 4.36; Co, 6.41; MoO₃, 73.85; H₂O, 13.07 per cent].

$$t = 27^\circ; \chi_g = 11.07 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_M = 12940 \times 10^{-6}; \chi_A = 13040 \times 10^{-6}; \mu_s = 5.60.$$

11. *Sodium Manganiv-paratungstate*.—Manganese chloride (MnCl₂·6H₂O, 1g.) and sodium paratungstate (10 g.) were dissolved in 50 c.c. of water and the mixture was heated to boiling. To this 4g. of sodium persulphate were added in small portions at a time to oxidise the mixture. It was then filtered from the insoluble residue of manganese dioxide. The dark red filtrate, on standing for some days, deposited fine prismatic needle-shaped crystals of deep red colour. These were purified by recrystallization from hot water (cf. Just, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3619). [Found: Na, 7.75; Mn,

3.16; WO_3 , 66.45; O(active), 0.90; H_2O (by diff.), 18.25. $3\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, MnO_2 , 5WO_3 , $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Na, 7.86; Mn, 3.13; WO_3 , 66.06; O(active), 0.91; H_2O , 18.44 per cent].

$t = 31.5^\circ$; $\chi_g = 2.96 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 5205 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_A = 53.2 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_n = 3.58$.

In making the diamagnetic correction, χ_g for MoO_3 was taken as $+0.0975 \times 10^{-6}$ at 31° , as determined in our laboratory; for, the values given by previous workers differ widely from one another. For WO_3 , χ_g value of 0.2×10^{-6} , given by Barkmann and Zocher (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 124, 318) for 15° , was used.

DISCUSSION

The two compounds, ammonium and barium nickel molybdate with quadrivalent nickel, are practically diamagnetic. The ammonium compound shows very slight paramagnetism, due possibly to the presence of some accidental impurities or slight decomposition. A quadrivalent nickel ion with six electrons in the $3d$ -level should show a strong paramagnetic moment corresponding to four unbalanced electrons, i.e., equal to about 5 Bohr magnetons from the Bose-Stoner's formula, $\mu_n = \sqrt{4S(S+1)}$, assuming that the orbital moments are completely quenched. Their diamagnetic character directly suggests that in these compounds the quadrivalent nickel atom constitutes the centre of a penetration complex with d^2sp^3 hybrid octahedral bonds. These substances are therefore, represented as molecular compounds of complex 6-molybdenum and 12-molybdenum heteropolyacid salts, or as a new 9-molybdenum complex, of the penetration type (*vide supra*).

Potassium cobaltic molybdates, compounds 2 and 3, as well as the ammonium salt of type 3, show also diamagnetism or very weak paramagnetic properties after diamagnetic correction. Obviously, the latter might be due to a slight decomposition, the pure substances being probably diamagnetic. Hence, the compounds must contain the trivalent cobalt as the central atom of a penetration complex with d^2sp^3 octahedral bonds. They should, therefore, be represented as containing a 6- or 5-molybdenum heteropoly complex anion as shown below:

Ammonium chromic molybdate gives a magnetic moment of about 4 Bohr magnetons, which might be attributed to the free chromic ion, or to the trivalent chromium forming the central atom of an octahedral co-ordination complex of the penetration type with d^2sp^3 bonds. The colour and stability of the compound in aqueous solution, even at the boiling temperature, justify its inclusion in the 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid complex of the latter type.

Ammonium ferric molybdate, on the other hand, shows a magnetic moment of 5.85 Bohr magnetons, characteristic of the ferric ion. Hence, the compound should be regarded as a 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid salt with the central ferric atom giving rise to a complex anion of the associated type with sp^3d^2 octahedral bonds, which might, therefore, resonate with ionic bonds.

Barium mangani-molybdate shows a magnetic moment of 3.88 Bohr magnetons, which is to be expected for a quadrivalent manganese ion, as also for an associated or penetration type of complex with octahedral bonds. From a consideration of its

physical and chemical properties, and its resemblance to the corresponding quadrivalent nickel compound in composition, we may represent its constitution similar to that of the latter :

Similar result has been obtained also for sodium manganii-paratungstate with quadrivalent manganese. It gives a magnetic moment value of 3.58 Bohr. It, therefore, contains a complex heteropolyacid anion, represented by the following formula,

Ammonium nickel^{II} and cupric molybdate give magnetic moments of 3.2 and 1.98 Bohr magnetons respectively. This is characteristic of bivalent nickel and copper ions. These two compounds, therefore, belong to the 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid complex of the associated type :

Magnetic moment values for ammonium manganous molybdate and ammonium cobaltous molybdate, which are 7 and 5.6 Bohr respectively, agree more or less with those for the bivalent manganese and cobalt ions. The moment value found for the manganese complex is rather unusually high, being 7 in place of 5.8 to 6.0 found for the simple manganous salts. This makes the purity of the product, or the accuracy of the measurement of its moment value, rather doubtful. The matter, therefore, deserves a fresh examination. Nevertheless, the results indicate that both the compounds belong to the 6-molybdenum heteropolyacid complex of the associated type, resonating with that of the ionic one :

Thus the determination of the magnetic properties of this interesting class of compounds furnishes confirmatory evidence in support of Rosenheim's view about their constitution, which represents them as salts of heteropoly molybdic (tungstic) acid with the metal atom forming the centre of the co-ordinated complex. They can be further distinguished into complexes of the penetration and associated type, as revealed by their magnetic and chemical properties.